

AI4

eOSC

Updated Data Management Plan

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¹ **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services),

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services),

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Prepared by	Reviewed by	Approved by
F. Aguilar	Á. López, V. Kozlov, G. Moltó, M. Plociennik	Project Management Board

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INTRODUCTION

The main objective of this deliverable is to update the status of the initial Data Management Plan, including the characteristics of the identified research artifacts that emerge from the project.

Although the focus of the DMP is to describe the way of handling data of the project use cases ([UC1 - Agrometeorological forecasts](#), [UC2 - Integrated plant protection](#), and [UC3 - Automated Thermography](#)) we are also including information of other relevant research outputs, including the AI modules developed by the use cases and delivered through the AI4EOSC platform. The modules are described and shared in such a way that allows the adoption of the FAIR principles, including metadata that details the models and enhances their reusability

Moreover, the project has carried out an open call² for new use cases. Although out of the scope for the initial DMP, we will invite the new use cases to participate in it in order to ensure a broader adoption of the FAIR principles and open data sharing in the EOSC context.

Besides, and in order to effectively ensure reproducibility, AI4EOSC is developing a metadata and provenance system to provide mode lineage and link any component related to the development of AI models. Supported by semantic technologies, the provenance system also supports the developments under a FAIR umbrella. Although not yet ready to be included in the DMP, we include initial information in this document, as a relevant piece of information or managing metadata within the project.

Lastly, in order to facilitate the tracking of the different research outputs, taking into account its dynamic and evolving nature, rather than providing a static document we have adopted the OpenAIRE ARGOS [\[3\]](#) service to keep an updated version of the data management plan. ARGOS is an open service developed by OpenAIRE to describe and manage data planning, supporting different DMP (Data Management Plan) templates (including the Horizon Europe one). This service was selected at the initial stage and it has been updated to include the current status. Thanks to the ARGOS features, the DMP is automatically exported and published in Zenodo. In this regard, it is worth to note that this deliverable does not contain the most updated Data Management Plan, that can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13302495> [\[1\]](#).

² <https://ai4eosc.eu/use-cases/first-open-call/>

USE CASES: RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Although the details about the different research outputs are included in the updated DMP in ARGOS [1], this section summarizes the type of datasets and data objects that are described in the online service (c.f. Figure 1). For the use cases that are part of the project consortium, at least one input dataset and one model are included as a descriptor fulfilling all the sections in the Horizon Europe DMP template. For those new use cases starting from the AI4EOOSC open call³, we will invite them to support the DMP providing information about their input data and models, updating the online DMP accordingly.

Figure 1: Screenshot of AI4EOOSC public DMP in ARGOS.

³ <https://ai4eosc.eu/use-cases/first-open-call/>

UC1 – AGROMETEOROLOGY

Anthropogenic-driven climate change is expected to affect, mainly to increase in, frequency and intensity of various types of extreme events. One of them is thunderstorms that generate adverse phenomena for farmers:

- High winds can break and damage buildings, equipment, materials and plants.
- Hail can cause leaf damage reducing yield or destroying plants, machines, cars, and buildings.
- Flash floods can endanger humans, and animals, damage machines and equipment, can lead to loss of topsoil as well as damage to crops.

In this use case radar imagery is processed utilizing AI ensemble stacking and federated learning to create added value products for improving farmers' activity, namely timely and precise warnings of thunderstorms for farmers. As an enhancement, the farmers want to know when exactly thunderstorms will hit their area so that they can get everyone to safety. Nowcasting can provide localized warnings around 30 minutes ahead of thunderstorms.

The model uses structured data (images and/or CSV) as input and the model code and weights are [available through the AI4EOSC platform](#)⁴.

The DMP includes two descriptors (Figures 2 and 3): one for the **input data**⁵ based on radar imagery and one for the available **AI module**⁶, which is ready to be reused within the AI4EOSC platform. The preprocessed data acting as input data for the model will be deposited at AI4EOSC's Zenodo community [5]. The AI module includes both the model as well as the DEEPaaS API packaged in a public Docker image ([ai4oshub/thunderstorm-nowcast-microstep](#)), which enables its reusability.

⁴ <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/thunderstorm-nowcast-microstep>

⁵ <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/619308a7-2965-48bb-aa0a-b8dcfd547b4c>

⁶ <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/6f6a3967-30a8-4863-b54f-4d5c42b7b81d>

Description UC1 – AGROMETEOROLOGY [Input Data]

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Part of

[AI4EOOSC Data Management Plan](#)

Grant

Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud

Researchers

 Fernando Aguilar Gómez (orcid:0000-0001-9462-4831)

Description

Anthropogenic-driven climate change is expected to affect, mainly to increase, frequency and intensity of various types of extreme events. One of them are thunderstorms that generate adverse phenomena for farmers:

- high winds can break and damage buildings, equipment, material and plants;
- hail can cause leaf damage reducing yield or destroying plants, machines, cars, and buildings;
- flash floods can endanger humans, animals, damage machines and equipment, can lead to loss of topsoil as well as damage to crops.

In this use case we process radar imagery - utilising AI ensemble stacking and federated learning - to create added value products for improving farmers activity, namely timely and precise warnings of thunderstorms for farmers. As an enhancement, the farmer wants to know when exactly thunderstorms will hit his area so that he can get everyone to safety. Nowcasting can provide localised warnings around 30 minutes ahead of thunderstorms. We integrated the use case with the platform, which enabled us to use existing AI model templates and state-of-the-art computing resources, perform automated testing and use other platform tools to tackle the problem. The model is a neural network currently, where the number of layers can be set by the user.

Figure 2: Screenshot of UC1 input data descriptor.

Description UC1 – AGROMETEOROLOGY [AI Module]

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[AI4EOOSC Data Management Plan](#)

Grant

Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud

Researchers

 Valentin Kozlov (orcid:0000-0002-8770-3619)

Description

Anthropogenic-driven climate change is expected to affect, mainly to increase, frequency and intensity of various types of extreme events. One of them are thunderstorms that generate adverse phenomena for farmers:

- high winds can break and damage buildings, equipment, material and plants;
- hail can cause leaf damage reducing yield or destroying plants, machines, cars, and buildings;
- flash floods can endanger humans, animals, damage machines and equipment, can lead to loss of topsoil as well as damage to crops.

In this use case we process radar imagery - utilising AI ensemble stacking and federated learning - to create added value products for improving farmers activity, namely timely and precise warnings of thunderstorms for farmers. As an enhancement, the farmer wants to know when exactly thunderstorms will hit his area so that he can get everyone to safety. Nowcasting can provide localised warnings around 30 minutes ahead of thunderstorms. We integrated the use case with the platform, which enabled us to use existing AI model templates and state-of-the-art computing resources, perform automated testing and use other platform tools to tackle the problem. The model is a neural network currently, where the number of layers can be set by the user.

Figure 3: Screenshot of UC1 AI module descriptor.

UC2 – INTEGRATED PLANT PROTECTION

This use case aims to determine the risk of disease in crops and determine the phases of plant growth and the condition of crops. The developed AI models are going to be integrated into existing national advisory platforms, operated by WODR and PSNC.

Currently, WODR and PSNC operate a national advisory platform for farmers (eDWIN), which includes a network of meteorological ground stations, the Farm Management System, and ground observations of the occurrence of diseases and pests. The current solutions are based on predictive mathematical models.

Within AI4EOSC, the goal is to enhance the existing mathematical prediction models based on machine and deep learning (ML/DL) for the early detection of plant diseases, while also integrating new data sources. The initial focus is on detection of the fungal disease occurrences in rye and sugar beet.

Ground observations of both plants are used as input for the training. There are different sources for these images, including datasets already available through the eDWIN project (<https://www.edwin.gov.pl/>), collected by the use case members (WODR and PSNC) or collected by partners collaborating with WODR in this aspect. In order to provide an analogous scenario in which the farmer wants to determine the disease, these field observations are being collected using cell phone cameras. The expected result is the development of a model that can determine whether the expected disease has shown symptoms.

The DMP includes two descriptors (Figures 4 and 5): one for the **input data**⁷ based on PNG plant images and one for the **available AI module**⁸, which is ready to be reused within the AI4EOSC platform via the [published module](#)⁹.

⁷ <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/619308a7-2965-48bb-aa0a-b8dcfd547b4c>

⁸ <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/6f6a3967-30a8-4863-b54f-4d5c42b7b81d>

⁹ <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/integrated-plant-protection>

Description

UC2 – INTEGRATED PLANT PROTECTION [Input Data]

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Part of

AI4EOSC Data Management Plan

Grant

Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud

Researchers

 [Ignacio Heredia \(orcid:0000-0001-6317-7100\)](#)

Description

The aim is to determine the risk of disease in agricultural crops and determine the phases of plant growth and the condition of crops. The developed AI models are going to be integrated into existing national advisory platforms, operated by WODR and PSNC.

Currently WODR and PSNC operate a national advisory platform for farmers (eDWIN), which includes a network of meteorological ground stations, the Farm Management System, and ground observations of the occurrence of diseases and pests. The current solutions are based on predictive mathematical models.

With AI4EOSC, the plan is to add to the current mathematical prediction models the ML/DL-based models used for early detection of the plant diseases and add new sources of the data. The initial focus is on detection of the fungal disease occurrences on rye and sugar beet.

Widely collected images of both plants are used as an input for the training. There are different sources of the images. Some come from other projects, some are being actively collected by our partners and some are collected by us. We are also near the end of getting the synthetic data which will supplement our training datasets. The expected result is the development of a model that can determine whether the expected disease has shown symptoms.

Figure 4: Screenshot of UC2 input data descriptor.

Description

UC2 – INTEGRATED PLANT PROTECTION [AI Module]

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Part of

AI4EOSC Data Management Plan

Grant

Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud

Researchers

 [Valentin Kozlov \(orcid:0000-0002-8770-3619\)](#)

Description

This use case aims to determine the risk of disease in crops and determine the phases of plant growth and the condition of crops. The developed AI models are going to be integrated into existing national advisory platforms, operated by WODR and PSNC.

Currently, WODR and PSNC operate a national advisory platform for farmers (eDWIN), which includes a network of meteorological ground stations, the Farm Management System, and ground observations of the occurrence of diseases and pests. The current solutions are based on predictive mathematical models.

With AI4EOSC, the plan is to add to the current mathematical prediction models the ML/DL-based models used for the early detection of plant diseases and add new sources of data. The initial focus is on detection of the fungal disease occurrences in rye and sugar beet.

Figure 5: Screenshot of UC2 AI module descriptor.

UC3 – AUTOMATED THERMOGRAPHY

Use case 3 leverages multispectral unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) based imaging and AI to identify “hot spots” (thermal anomalies) in urban settings and thus improve the efficiency of energy-related systems. The two scenarios being examined are:

- Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detection (TBBRDet): Detecting thermal hotspots on building rooftops caused by thermal bridges to support urban planners and building owners with retrofitting plans.
- Thermal Urban Feature Segmentation (TUFSeg): Detecting thermal hotspots caused by common urban features (cars, manholes, streetlamps, etc.) to aid district heating network operators in their search for pipeline leakages by automatically removing these false alarms from the list of potential suspects.

The utilized data is given in the form of multispectral imagery, simultaneously acquired standard red green blue (RGB) and thermal infrared (TIR) images. Via custom processing pipelines, this raw data is undistorted, aligned and merged into 4-channel images. Selected images are annotated with the Visual Geometry Group (VGG) Image Annotator, thus creating JSON files. In preparation for AI model training, these are processed according to formats required by the utilized methods and toolboxes. Both scenarios are developing its model to be added to AI4EOSC ecosystem.

The DMP includes four descriptors (Figures 6, 7, 8, and 9): two for the **input data**¹⁰¹¹ based on the aforementioned scenarios and two for the **available AI modules**¹²¹³. There are two datasets for the TBBR model already available at Zenodo (raw [6] and processed [7]), while the TUFSeg dataset is a draft and will be published whenever possible. That is why datasets from the two models are included as descriptors as well as two different models, for thermal bridges detection and thermal urban feature segmentation.

¹⁰ <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/59b97db8-e43c-48e3-ab36-c243e077a4be>

¹¹ <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/9e4b2f17-8d52-4192-9db1-7b4b7fde745b>

¹² <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/234dd961-f5fa-45be-8888-cc65bdc4c362>

¹³ <https://argos.openaire.eu/datasets/overview/c0f53fad-b7fd-43fb-b92c-c29f0ca92633>

Description **UC3 – AUTOMATED THERMOGRAPHY [Input data - TUFSeg]**

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Part of

[AI4EOSC Data Management Plan](#)

Grant

Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud

Researchers

 Fernando Aguilar Gómez (orcid:0000-0001-9462-4831)

Description

Use case 3 leverages multispectral unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) based imaging and AI to identify "hot spots" (thermal anomalies) in urban settings and thus improve the efficiency of energy-related systems. One of the two scenarios being examined is:

Thermal Urban Feature Segmentation (TUFSeg): Detecting thermal hotspots caused by common urban features (cars, manholes, streetlamps, etc.) to aid district heating network operators in their search for pipeline leakages by automatically removing these false alarms from the list of potential suspects.

Figure 6: Screenshot of UC3 input data (TufSeg) descriptor.

Description **UC3 – AUTOMATED THERMOGRAPHY [Input data - TBBRDet]**

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[AI4EOSC Data Management Plan](#)

Grant

Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud

Researchers

 Valentin Kozlov (orcid:0000-0002-8770-3619)

Description

Use case 3 leverages multispectral unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) based imaging and AI to identify "hot spots" (thermal anomalies) in urban settings and thus improve the efficiency of energy-related systems. One of the two scenarios being examined is described in this description.

Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detection (TBBRDet): Detecting thermal hotspots on building rooftops caused by thermal bridges to support urban planners and building owners with retrofitting plans.

The utilized data is given in the form of multispectral imagery, simultaneously acquired standard red green blue (RGB) and thermal infrared (TIR) images. Via custom processing pipelines, this raw data is undistorted, aligned and merged into 4-channel images. Select images are annotated with the VGG Image Annotator, thus creating JSON files. In preparation for AI model training, these are processed according to formats required by the utilized methods and toolboxes.

Figure 7: Screenshot of UC3 input data (TBBRDet) descriptor.

Description UC3 – AUTOMATED THERMOGRAPHY [AI module - TUFSeg]

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Grant

Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud

Researchers

 Álvaro López García (orcid:0000-0002-0013-4602)

Description

Use case 3 leverages multispectral unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) based imaging and AI to identify "hot spots" (thermal anomalies) in urban settings and thus improve the efficiency of energy-related systems. One of the two scenarios being examined is:

- Thermal Urban Feature Segmentation (TUFSeg): Detecting thermal hotspots caused by common urban features (cars, manholes, streetlamps, etc.) to aid district heating network operators in their search for pipeline leakages by automatically removing these false alarms from the list of potential suspects.

Figure 8: Screenshot of UC3 AI module (TUFSeg) descriptor.

Description UC3 – AUTOMATED THERMOGRAPHY [AI module - TBBRDet]

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Grant

Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud

Researchers

 Fernando Aguilar Gómez (orcid:0000-0001-9462-4831)

Description

Use case 3 leverages multispectral unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) based imaging and AI to identify "hot spots" (thermal anomalies) in urban settings and thus improve the efficiency of energy-related systems. One of the two scenarios being examined is:

- Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detection (TBBRDet): Detecting thermal hotspots on building rooftops caused by thermal bridges to support urban planners and building owners with retrofitting plans.

Figure 9: Screenshot of UC3 AI module (TBBRDet) descriptor.

DMP QUESTIONNAIRE - HORIZON EUROPE TEMPLATE

The Horizon Europe Data Management Plan (DMP) Template [2] is an essential tool for researchers and project managers involved in Horizon Europe projects. This template ensures that the management of research data aligns with the principles and requirements of Horizon Europe, promoting transparency, accessibility, and reuse. Although it is not mandatory to follow this template, the list of sections is complete enough to describe all the characteristics of the research outputs from AI4EOSC and its use cases. The following subsections describe the sections on the DMP template that have been filled by AI4EOSC use cases and the approach taken to complete the required information.

SECTIONS OF THE HORIZON EUROPE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN TEMPLATE

Although the AI4EOSC use cases differ in their aims, types of data and model architecture, they are similar in terms of the types of research artifacts to be described. For each of the use cases, at least the input data and model are described separately, taking into account their characteristics. To complete the list of sections as well as providing the proper details taking into account each type of research output, the template including specific tips for the particular object was sent to the use case managers. Once the first iteration is completed, the information has been introduced in the ARGOS service [3] and checked by the managers, who keep the information updated.

Data Summary

Apart from the description of the use case that includes necessary information about the input data and model goals for each of the use cases, this section describes different characteristics of the research output like the format selected to be shared, the utility of the asset or the estimated size. Since one of the AI4EOSC objectives is to facilitate the reuse of AI models, both data and models/code are packaged to enable the sharing.

FAIR Data

The FAIR data principles [4] –Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability—are crucial for effective data management and to facilitate the understanding of the produced research outputs.

Making Data Findable

Researchers must ensure that data can be easily found by others. This includes using persistent identifiers for the data, providing rich metadata to enable

discovery, and using appropriate keywords to optimize searchability. Metadata should be made available in a way that allows it to be harvested and indexed.

Although most of the potential research outputs are already available through the platform, AI4EOSC aims to share its research outputs not only in the platform but also in relevant open repositories. The first target repository to increase the visibility is [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/)¹⁴, so part of the research outputs are already available at AI4EOSC community [5] and some others will be shortly. Furthermore, some developments within the AI4EOSC are oriented to integrate the platform with Zenodo, for example for packaging the code repositories and models to be automatically published in Zenodo via the platform wide quality assurance pipeline [8].

Making Data Accessible

This involves depositing data in trusted repositories and ensuring open access wherever possible. If data cannot be shared openly, researchers need to explain why, distinguish between legal, contractual, and intentional restrictions, and describe if access to the data, even not open, can be granted on a case-by-case scenario. In cases where an embargo period is applied, its duration and justification must be specified. The plan should also describe how access to data will be provided during and after the project, including any necessary authentication procedures and the potential need for a data access committee.

Following this idea and given the Zenodo features, it supports the accessibility within AI4EOSC.

Making Data Interoperable

Researchers should use standard data and metadata formats and vocabularies to ensure that data can be exchanged and reused across different disciplines. They need to follow community-endorsed best practices for interoperability and provide mappings to commonly used ontologies if they use project-specific vocabularies.

Zenodo is limited in the use of interoperable features, due to the fact that it is a multidisciplinary repository. It includes some features that allow semantic and linked data, but the use of disciplinary metadata schemas is not currently available. However, given the EOSC context and the developments of AI4EOSC, some efforts are being made to increase interoperability. The model provenance system, described below in a dedicated section, enables different mechanisms to facilitate interoperability, like the identification of different components along the model design and training and the establishment of particular relationships among those elements.

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

Increasing Data Re-use

Documentation is vital to validate data analysis and facilitate reuse. This includes providing README files, codebooks, and other relevant information. Data should be made freely available using free and open licenses (by default the AI4EOSC consortium has adopted the CC-BY license [9]). The data provenance must be thoroughly documented, and data quality assurance processes should be described. In a few use cases, the input data is already created or available in different sources. In the cases where derived data is generated, proper licenses will be selected, always taking into account the particularities in terms of sensitivity.

AI4EOSC aims at enabling the reuse of models, so the components involved in the creation of a model should be shared to facilitate that reuse. Furthermore, some of the models include support documentation like codebooks and they are packaged in Docker images. Within the AI4EOSC platform, free and open licenses (such as Apache 2, GPL-3 or MIT) have been selected to share the components and the EOSC context will also facilitate that goal. The final license adoption is a developer choice, upon approval of the Project Management Board.

Allocation of Resources

This section requires a detailed plan for the resources needed to make data and other research outputs FAIR. Researchers must outline the costs related to storage, archiving, reuse, and security, and how these costs will be covered. They should identify who will be responsible for data management and how long-term preservation will be ensured, including the necessary resources and decision-making processes. Although the main benefit of AI4EOSC to enable the sharing of the developed models is the platform and, in particular the marketplace, alternatives should be planned for potential interruptions in the maintenance. Apart from finding ways to keep the AI4EOSC developments even after the project ends, the research outputs are shared in different formats, including packages of data, code and models in Zenodo, code at GitHub or Docker images, which are publicly stored at Docker Hub and in the AI4EOSC container registry for platform usage and long-term preservation. Zenodo, supported by different research institutions and funding programs, is expected to maintain the outputs in the long term, so no direct costs are expected to be dedicated.

Data Security

Researchers need to detail the provisions in place for data security, including measures for data recovery, secure storage, archiving, and the transfer of sensitive data. For the described use case, the input data is at least in a NextCloud within the AI4EOSC ecosystem, which includes the standard measurements of data integrity and security. In some of the cases, the data is already published on Zenodo, having two separate systems to avoid data loss.

The code from the models is managed in GitHub, including versioning and branch development, which facilitate the tracking. Also, the repositories are integrated into the DevOps tools, which enables their quality and anticipates any potential security problem.

Ethics & Other Issues

Given the nature of the AI4EOSC data and models, there are not any special considerations to be adopted from the ethics point of view. For the UC3 involving drone flights, the imagery includes geographical coordinates and therefore contains certain location information, but no people or cars are identifiable through the data.

ARGOS

ARGOS, developed through a collaboration between OpenAIRE and EUDAT, provides an open platform for Data Management Planning. It aligns with FAIR and Open best practices, presenting no barriers to use and adoption. ARGOS is available as a standalone service (OpenDMP) and as an OpenAIRE service (ARGOS), simplifying the management, validation, monitoring, and maintenance of Data Management Plans. Researchers, managers, and supervisors can create actionable DMPs that are freely exchangeable among infrastructures, facilitating various aspects of the data management process in accordance with the data owners' intentions and commitments.

The updated and online DMP is published with DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13302495](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13302495). A screenshot of the online service was provided in [Figure 1](#).

METADATA IN AI4EOSC PLATFORM

AI4 METADATA

Given the heterogeneity of the use cases and models involved in AI4EOSC, the platform requires a common layer to define the characteristics of the different applications. The use of generic metadata allows users to find available models which are indexed in the system thanks to tags, descriptions or typologies. All the AI modules have in common that their code is available on GitHub, the data is available in either public or private data repositories and there is a containerized version on Docker Hub.

In order to represent the characteristics of the models available in the marketplace, a set of metadata has been created in the JSON schema. The new version of the metadata structure includes this list of items:

- Title, description, summary
- DOI of the data science application
- Documentation, source code, docker image and dataset links
- How the model should be cited
- Creation and update dates
- Libraries involved (e.g. *TensorFlow*, *Keras*, etc.)
- The type of task the model does (e.g. *Classification*, *Clustering*, *Uncertainty Estimation*, etc.)
- Platform Category (i.e. *AI4 pre trained*, *AI4 trainable*, *AI4 inference* or *AI4 tools*)
- Type of data that the model utilizes (e.g. *Image*, *Text*, *Time Series*, etc.)

A set of metadata tools, along with the different metadata versions are available in the [AI4 Metadata Tools repository](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13343453) and are published in Zenodo with DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13343453](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13343453).

This new version of the metadata is parsed by the platform and will be rendered in the dashboard (and marked with Microdata tags) in a user-friendly way, to show all the characteristics that define a model. This supports the accessibility of the model and facilitates its findability.

MODEL PROVENANCE & FAIRNESS

One of the keys for ensuring the FAIRness along the different components involved to develop an AI model is to identify them and establish properly its relationships. Given the AI4EOSC architecture supported by different modules that enables the automatic management of the platform, a set of developments are in progress to track the provenance information. They are divided in three main components:

- ai4-prov¹⁵: generic repository linking to the different modules.
- ai4-prov-fetcher¹⁶: extracts the information from different components in the architecture.
- ai4-prov-tracker¹⁷: manage the provenance fragments for storing and composing provenance information.
- ai4-prov-viz¹⁸: enables an interactive visualization of the complete provenance graph to show its components and relationships.

Although the model provenance is not part of the DMP itself, it supports the collection of information for enriching the documentation and, in particular, the metadata, providing a system based on ontologies and semantic technologies to improve the FAIRness of the AI4EOSC research outputs.

¹⁵ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-prov>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-prov-fetcher>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-prov-tracker>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-prov-viz>

CONCLUSIONS

The content of this deliverable “D1.4 - Updated Data Management Plan” is the extension of the Initial DMP and summarizes the approach for ensuring the FAIRness of the research outputs derived from AI4EOSC.

Rather than being the DMP itself, D1.4 presents the structure to be found in the ARGOS system [\[1\]](#), where all the different data components and research outputs are described, including input data from the different Use Cases as well as the developed AI models. This way, we can ensure that the final DMP of the AI4EOSC project contains up to date information and it can be continuously updated. This document also describes some examples of the information that can be found in ARGOS, and how generic decisions have been taken.

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